

A SIMPLIFIED METHOD FOR DETERMINING THE STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE COMPONENTS OF FREE-EDGE DELAMINATIONS IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

A simplified method for determining the individual mode components of the strain energy release rate of free-edge delaminations in composite laminates is proposed. Interlaminar stresses are evaluated as an interface moment and interface shear forces. A edge-delaminated laminate is analyzed by using a generalized quasi-three dimensional classical laminated plate theory developed by the authors. The analysis provides closed-form expressions for the Mode-I, Mode-II, and Mode-III component of the strain energy release rate. Comparison of the results with a finite element analysis using the virtual crack closure technique shows good agreement.

INTRODUCTION

Delaminations along the free edges of composite laminates under uniform axial strain as shown in Fig. 1 have been observed during testing and in service. The free-edge delaminations induce redistribution of the stresses in the plies of the laminate, and, therefore, usually result in a reduction of stiffness and strength of the laminate. A number of experimental and analytical investigations have been directed toward well understanding free-edge delamination mechanisms. Pipes and Pagano [1] proposed a quasi-three dimensional (Q3D) analysis for a symmetric laminate under uniform axial extension. They showed the interlaminar stress distribution by the finite difference technique based on the Q3D analysis, and pointed out that the free-edge delaminations are caused by the interlaminar stresses which arise in the vicinity of the free edge. Rybicki, Schmueser and Fox [2] and Wang and Crossman [3] evaluated the strain energy release rate (SERR) by using a finite element method (FEM) with the virtual crack closure technique. These previous works have shown that the delamination onset and growth can be characterized quantitatively by the SERR. In order to estimate the SERR, O'Brien [4] developed a simple expression based on the classical laminated plate theory (CLT) and the rule of mixtures. Aoki and Kondo [5] proposed a method based on the J-integral law in combination with the CLT for calculating the Mode-I component of SERR. Armanios and Rehfield [6] used a sublaminar analysis with a shear deformable plate theory to determine the individual mode components of SERR. Schapery and Davidson [7] proposed a crack tip element approach, which is a method combined a sublaminar analysis based on the CLT with FEM, for determining mode ratio of SERR. Kunoo, Uda, Ono and Onohara [8] presented a generalized

Figure 1. A laminate with free-edge delaminations and coordinate system.

quasi-three dimensional classical laminated plate theory (GQ3D-CLT) to obtain the SERR.

The objective of the present work is to develop a simplified method for determining the individual mode components of SERR. The method is based on the GQ3D-CLT. The analysis provides closed-form expressions for the Mode-I, Mode-II, and Mode-III component of SERR.

Figure 2. Definition of interface moment and interface shear forces.

FORMULATION

EVALUATION OF INTERLAMINAR STRESSES

Classical laminated plate theory (CLT) assumes that the state of stress within each lamina of a multidirectional laminate is planar. This assumption is accurate for inner regions removed from laminate geometric discontinuities, such as free edge. In the vicinity of the free edge a boundary exists where the state of stress is three dimensional. The boundary width is approximately equal to the overall laminate thickness [1]. The stresses which arise at the interface between adjacent layers in the boundary are called interlaminar stresses. A lot of studies have been made to analyze the distribution of the interlaminar stresses. In this paper, we evaluate indirectly the interlaminar stresses as stress resultants instead of calculating the interlaminar stress distribution.

CLT gives the inplane stresses, σ_y and τ_{xy} shown in Fig. 2. These inplane stresses vanish at the free edge of the laminate. By using equilibrium equations of stress resultants at the interface $z = z_i$ in the boundary, we define an interface moment [9] $m(z_i)$ and interface shear forces $q_y(z_i)$ and $q_x(z_i)$ as follows.

$$m(z_i) = \int_{z_i}^{h/2} \sigma_y(z) z dz, \quad q_y(z_i) = - \int_{z_i}^{h/2} \sigma_y(z) dz, \quad q_x(z_i) = - \int_{z_i}^{h/2} \tau_{xy}(z) dz \quad (1)$$

The interface moment $m(z_i)$ is reacted by the interlaminar normal stress component σ_z . The distribution of the interlaminar normal stress must therefore result in zero vertical force vector while producing a moment equal in magnitude to that given by the first equation of Eqn (1). When the interface moment is positive, the interlaminar normal stress σ_z is tensile in the boundary near the free edge. It means that a peeling stress occurs at the interface in the free-edge boundary and delamination crack with the opening mode (Mode I) may be generated.

The interface shear forces, $q_y(z_i)$ and $q_x(z_i)$, are reacted by the interlaminar shear stress components τ_{yz} and τ_{xz} , respectively. When the interface shear force is not zero, the interlaminar shear stress occurs at the interface in the free-edge boundary. In the case of $q_y(z_i) \neq 0$, delamination crack with the in-plane shear mode (Mode II) may be generated. In the case of $q_x(z_i) \neq 0$, delamination crack with the anti-plane shear mode (Mode III) may be generated.

GENERALIZED QUASI-THREE DIMENSIONAL CLASSICAL LAMINATED PLATE THEORY

Pipes and Pagano [1] proposed the following quasi-three dimensional (Q3D) displacement field equations for symmetric laminates under uniform axial strain as shown in Fig. 3.

$$u(x, y, z) = U(y, z) + \epsilon_0 x, \quad v(x, y, z) = V(y, z), \quad w(x, y, z) = W(y, z) \quad (2)$$

where ϵ_0 is uniform axial strain. These Q3D displacement field equations, however, are not

Figure 3. Quasi-three dimensional problem.

Figure 4. Generalized quasi-three dimensional problem.

applicable to unsymmetric laminates. Hence we derived the following displacement field equations for unsymmetric laminates [8].

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y, z) &= U(y, z) + (C_1 + C_4y + C_2z) x , \\ v(x, y, z) &= V(y, z) - \frac{1}{2} (C_4x - C_3z) x , \\ w(x, y, z) &= W(y, z) - \frac{1}{2} (C_2x + C_3y) x . \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

We called these displacement field equations generalized quasi-three dimensional (GQ3D) displacement field equations. While the parameter C_1 is equivalent to ϵ_0 , which describes uniform axial strain of a laminate, the GQ3D equations include additional parameters C_2 , C_3 , and C_4 . C_2 and C_4 represent bending deformations of a laminate, and C_3 represents twisting deformation of a laminate.

We derive a generalized quasi-three dimensional classical laminated plate theory (GQ3D-CLT) by applying the GQ3D displacement field equations (3) to CLT. CLT gives the in-plane strain components of a laminate as follows.

$$\epsilon_x = \epsilon_x^0 + z\kappa_x , \quad \epsilon_y = \epsilon_y^0 + z\kappa_y , \quad \gamma_{xy} = \gamma_{xy}^0 + z\kappa_{xy} . \quad (4)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_x^0 &= \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} , & \epsilon_y^0 &= \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} , & \gamma_{xy}^0 &= \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} , \\ \kappa_x &= -\frac{\partial^2 w^0}{\partial x^2} , & \kappa_y &= -\frac{\partial^2 w^0}{\partial y^2} , & \kappa_{xy} &= -2 \frac{\partial^2 w^0}{\partial x \partial y} . \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

u^0 , v^0 , and w^0 are displacements at the midplane of the laminate. On the other hand, we get the following x -direction strain by the use of the GQ3D displacement field equations (3).

$$\epsilon_x = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = C_1 + C_4y + C_2z \quad (6)$$

Comparing Eqn (6) with Eqn (4), we obtain the following relations.

$$C_1 + C_4y = \epsilon_x^0 , \quad C_2 = \kappa_x \quad (7)$$

We consider the laminate under uniform axial strain ϵ_0 . Therefore,

$$C_1 = \epsilon_0 \quad (8)$$

Introducing the curvature ω_x with respect to the bending moment around the z axis acting at the yz plane, we get the following equation.

$$C_4 = \omega_x \quad (9)$$

Substituting the GQ3D displacement field equations (3) to the last equation of Eqn (5), we obtain

$$C_3 = \kappa_{xy} \quad (10)$$

We can find that the GQ3D displacement field equations (3) are applicable to analyzing a laminate under the bending deformations, κ_x and ω_x , and the twisting deformation κ_{xy} , in addition to axial extension ϵ_0 , as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 5. Resultant forces and moments acting on a laminate with finite width.

CLT defines forces and moments per unit width because of the infinite plate assumption of CLT. In the GQ3D-CLT, however, we employ the following definitions for the resultant forces and moments acting on the laminate with finite width as shown in Fig. 5, introducing a resultant moment T_x corresponding to the curvature ω_x .

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} &= \int_{z_1}^{z_2} \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} dy dz, \quad \begin{Bmatrix} M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \int_{z_1}^{z_2} \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} z dy dz, \\ T_x &= \int_{z_1}^{z_2} \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \sigma_x y dy dz. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The stress-strain relations for the k -th layer of a multilayered laminate can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}_k &= \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix}_k \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix}_k \left(\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_0 \\ \epsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} + z \begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} + y \begin{Bmatrix} \omega_x \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Substituting Eqn (12) to Eqn (11), we can get the following constitutive equations for the GQ3D-CLT.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \\ T_x \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & C_{11} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & C_{12} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & C_{16} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} & E_{11} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} & E_{12} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} & E_{16} \\ C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{16} & E_{11} & E_{12} & E_{16} & F_{11} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_0 \\ \epsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \\ \omega_x \end{Bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} [A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij}] &= (y_2 - y_1) \sum_{k=1}^N (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k \left[(z_k - z_{k-1}), \frac{1}{2} (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2), \frac{1}{3} (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3) \right] \\ [C_{ij}, E_{ij}] &= \frac{1}{2} (y_2^2 - y_1^2) \sum_{k=1}^N (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k \left[(z_k - z_{k-1}), \frac{1}{2} (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2) \right] \\ F_{11} &= \frac{1}{3} (y_2^3 - y_1^3) \sum_{k=1}^N (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (z_k - z_{k-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

ANALYSIS OF A LAMINATE WITH A FREE-EDGE DELAMINATION BY GQ3D-CLT

We consider a laminate with a free-edge delamination under uniform axial strain, as shown in Fig. 6. The laminate is divided into three sublaminates. The delamination length is denoted by a . Sublaminates 2 and 3 represent the groups of plies below and above the interface along which delamination occurs, respectively. Because the forces, N_y and N_{xy} , and the moment, M_y , are not reacted on the laminate under uniform axial strain, the following conditions should be satisfied for each sublaminates.

Figure 6. Sublaminates description.

$$N_y^{(\ell)} = N_{xy}^{(\ell)} = M_y^{(\ell)} = 0 \tag{15}$$

where superscript (ℓ) denotes the ℓ -th sublaminates. Hence we get the following reduced constitutive equations for the ℓ -th sublaminates.

$$\tilde{N}^{(\ell)} = \tilde{H}^{(\ell)} \tilde{C}^{(\ell)} \tag{16}$$

where

$$\tilde{N}^{(\ell)} = \begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ M_x \\ M_{xy} \\ T_x \end{Bmatrix}^{(\ell)}, \quad \tilde{H}^{(\ell)} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & B_{11} & B_{16} & C_{11} \\ B_{11} & D_{11} & D_{16} & E_{11} \\ B_{16} & D_{16} & D_{66} & E_{16} \\ C_{11} & E_{11} & E_{16} & F_{11} \end{bmatrix}^{(\ell)}, \quad \tilde{C}^{(\ell)} = \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_0 \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_{xy} \\ \omega_x \end{Bmatrix}^{(\ell)} \tag{17}$$

The vectors $\tilde{C}^{(1)}$, $\tilde{C}^{(2)}$, and $\tilde{C}^{(3)}$, which describe deformation of each sublaminates, can be proved to be equal since the displacements of each sublaminates are the same at the interface between the adjacent sublaminates. In addition, it is clear that the force and the moments reacted on the whole of the laminate are equal to the sums of the corresponding force and moments on each sublaminates. Hence we obtain the following reduced constitutive equation for the whole of the laminate.

$$\tilde{N}^{LAM} = \tilde{H}^{LAM} \tilde{C}^{LAM} \tag{18}$$

where

$$\tilde{N}^{LAM} = \tilde{N}^{(1)} + \tilde{N}^{(2)} + \tilde{N}^{(3)}, \quad \tilde{H}^{LAM} = \tilde{H}^{(1)} + \tilde{H}^{(2)} + \tilde{H}^{(3)}, \quad \tilde{C}^{LAM} = \tilde{C}^{(1)} = \tilde{C}^{(2)} = \tilde{C}^{(3)} \tag{19}$$

Superscript *LAM* denotes the whole of the laminate.

We get deformation of each sublaminates by solving the constitutive equation (18). Substituting $\tilde{C}^{(1)}$, $\tilde{C}^{(2)}$, and $\tilde{C}^{(3)}$ to Eqn (16) and using Eqn (15), we can obtain strains and curvature, $\epsilon_y^{0(\ell)}$, $\gamma_{xy}^{0(\ell)}$ and $\kappa_y^{(\ell)}$, of each sublaminates from Eqn (13) written in terms of the ℓ -th sublaminates.

SIMPLIFIED METHOD FOR DETERMINING STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE COMPONENTS OF A FREE-EDGE DELAMINATION

We can get the strain-energy release per unit length of the laminate caused by the introduction of a delamination crack of length a as follows.

$$U(a) = \frac{1}{2} (N_x^{LAM} \epsilon_0^{LAM} + M_x^{LAM} \kappa_x^{LAM} + M_{xy}^{LAM} \kappa_{xy}^{LAM} + T_x^{LAM} \omega_x^{LAM}) \tag{20}$$

We obtain the following equation for the total strain energy release rate under the constant displacement condition.

$$G(a) = - \frac{U(a + \Delta a) - U(a)}{\Delta a} \quad (21)$$

where Δa is a virtual crack extension length.

As we mentioned before, a peeling stress occurs at the interface $z = z_i$ in the free-edge boundary when the interface moment $m(z_i)$ is positive. If a delamination crack of length a with the opening mode (Mode I) is generated, we can calculate the opening angle of the crack by $(\kappa_y^{(3)} - \kappa_y^{(2)})a$, where $\kappa_y^{(3)}$ and $\kappa_y^{(2)}$ represent the curvature of sublaminates above and below the interface $z = z_i$ along which delamination occurs, respectively. We get the Mode-I strain energy release by the introduction of the delamination crack as follows.

$$U_I(a) = \frac{1}{2} m(z_i) (\kappa_y^{(3)} - \kappa_y^{(2)}) a \quad (22)$$

We can obtain the inplane sliding displacement of the crack by $(\epsilon_y^{0(3)} - \epsilon_y^{0(2)})a$, and the anti-plane tearing displacement of the crack by $(\gamma_{xy}^{0(3)} - \gamma_{xy}^{0(2)})a$ as well. Using the interface shear forces $q_y(z_i)$ and $q_x(z_i)$, we get the Mode-II and Mode-III strain energy release due to the introduction of the delamination crack by the following equations, respectively.

$$U_{II}(a) = \frac{1}{2} q_y(z_i) (\epsilon_y^{0(3)} - \epsilon_y^{0(2)}) a, \quad U_{III}(a) = \frac{1}{2} q_x(z_i) (\gamma_{xy}^{0(3)} - \gamma_{xy}^{0(2)}) a \quad (23)$$

We can therefore calculate the Mode-I, Mode-II, and Mode-III component of SERR for the free-edge delamination of length a by the following equations, respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} G_I(a) &= U_I(a)/a = \frac{1}{2} m(z_i) (\kappa_y^{(3)} - \kappa_y^{(2)}) \\ G_{II}(a) &= U_{II}(a)/a = \frac{1}{2} q_y(z_i) (\epsilon_y^{0(3)} - \epsilon_y^{0(2)}) \\ G_{III}(a) &= U_{III}(a)/a = \frac{1}{2} q_x(z_i) (\gamma_{xy}^{0(3)} - \gamma_{xy}^{0(2)}) \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

The proposed method is applied to determine the mode components of SERR for free-edge delaminations in a $[30/-30/90]_5$ composite laminate under uniform axial extension. The material properties and the geometry of the laminate are given in Table 1. Free-edge delaminations exist at the interfaces which are symmetrically located with respect to the $z = 0$ plane (midplane) and the $y = 0$ plane as shown in Fig. 1. Because of symmetries, only one quarter of the $x = 0$ section was analyzed. We utilized a generalized quasi-three dimensional finite element method [8] with the virtual crack closure technique to evaluate the accuracy of the present simplified method. The FEM code uses eight-node quadrilateral isoparametric elements.

Table 1. Material properties and geometry of the laminate.

$E_L = 138.6$ GPa	$E_T = 10.07$ GPa
$G_{LT} = 4.117$ GPa	$G_{TT} = 3.873$ GPa
$\nu_{LT} = 0.3200$	$\nu_{TT} = 0.3000$
b (Semi-width) = 15 mm	
h (Laminate thickness) = $6h_0 = 0.84$ mm	
h_0 (Ply thickness) = 0.14 mm	

L denotes the fiber direction and
 T denotes the transverse direction.

Most analyses to obtain the SERR for composite laminates with delamination assume that individual plies or ply groups may be modeled as homogeneous and orthotropic. When this assumption is adopted and the delamination is

between plies at dissimilar angles, a linear elastic analysis will predict a near-field oscillatory singularity to exist and the individual SERR components cannot be uniquely defined [10]. Raju, Crews and Aminpour [10] analyzed the individual SERR components by the finite element model with a thin resin layer at the delamination interface to eliminate the oscillatory singularity. They showed that the finite element model with the 'bare' interface, where the resin layer does not exist, is a very good approximation to the case with the interface resin layer, when the virtual crack extension length Δa is either 0.25 or 0.5 of the ply thickness h_0 . Hence we took $\Delta a / h_0 = 0.36$ in FEM.

We analyzed two cases, that is (a) $[30/-30/90]_S$ laminate with delaminations at the 90/90 interface and (b) $[30/-30/90]_S$ laminate with delaminations at the 30/-30 interfaces.

(a) $[30/-30/90]_S$ Laminate with Delaminations at the 90/90 Interface

Figure 7 shows the SERR for $[30/-30/90]_S$ laminate with delaminations at the 90/90 interface. The abscissa is the delamination crack length, and the ordinate is the SERR normalized by the square of the uniform axial strain ϵ_0 . The total SERR G calculated by Eqn (21) coincides with the Mode-I SERR G_I obtained by the first equation of Eqn (24). The Mode-II and Mode-III SERR calculated from Eqn (24) are zero. The Mode-I component of SERR obtained by the present method is identical to the FEM with the virtual crack closure technique, when the delamination length is approximately more than the laminate thickness and when the delamination length is not too long. The SERR obtained from the FEM decreases as the delamination almost grows up across the laminate width.

(b) $[30/-30/90]_S$ Laminate with Delaminations at the 30/-30 Interfaces

Figure 8 shows the individual components of SERR for $[30/-30/90]_S$ laminate with delaminations at the 30/-30 interfaces. The Mode-I, Mode-II, and Mode-III component of SERR calculated by Eqn (24) are in well agreement with the FEM, when the delamination length is approximately more than the laminate thickness and when the delamination length is not too long. The mode components of SERR obtained from the FEM decrease as the delamination almost grows up across the laminate width. The total SERR calculated by Eqn (21) coincides with the FEM when the delamination length is not too short or long.

Figure 7. Strain energy release rate for $[30/-30/90]_S$ laminate with free-edge delaminations at the 90/90 interface.

Figure 8. Strain energy release rate for $[30/-30/90]_S$ laminate with free-edge delaminations at the 30/-30 interfaces.

DISCUSSION

Wang [11] showed that the SERR increases to a maximum value with increasing delamination length, beyond which it remains constant. He called the delamination length at which this transition occurs as a characteristic delamination length. When predicting the onset and growth of free-edge delaminations, it is becoming relatively accepted to determine the SERR for a delamination of the characteristic length or greater, and then to compare the calculated SERR to the critical value. The present method gives a good estimation the individual components of SERR for the delamination of the characteristic length or greater.

The present method does not need the near-field information such as the displacement field or the distribution of the interlaminar stresses. Hence this method is not concerned with the oscillatory singularity. And, the analysis provides closed-form expressions for the Mode-I, Mode-II, and Mode-III component of SERR. The simple nature of the method makes it suitable for primary design analysis for the delaminations of composite laminates.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the previous sections, the following conclusions can be drawn.

1. A simplified method for determining the mode components of the strain energy release rate (SERR) of free-edge delaminations in composite laminates was developed. The method is based on a generalized quasi-three dimensional analysis modified the classical laminated plate theory. The analysis provides closed-form expressions for the Mode-I, Mode-II, and Mode-III component of SERR.
2. The individual mode components of SERR obtained by the present method are in good agreement with a finite element analysis using the virtual crack closure technique.

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